

A Line Spectrum Approach for the Design of Optimum Compaction FIR Filters

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we propose a new design method for optimal compaction gain FIR filters of a finite order. Starting from the odd polyphase component $r(1), r(3), \dots, r(2K - 1)$ of the input correlation sequence we find a suitable extension to an infinite sequence $r_e(k)$, such that the corresponding spectrum $S_e(\omega)$ is a line spectrum with K_1 ($K_1 \leq (K + 1)/2$) lines. In quite general conditions it is possible to design the optimal compaction filter $H(e^{j\omega})$ of order $2K - 1$ such that it has zeros at the line frequencies of $S_e(\omega)$ and $|H(e^{j\omega})|^2$ obeys the Nyquist(2) condition. The analytical method presented in [1] can be easily shown to be a particular case in this framework, but our method finds the optimal solution in some of the cases when [1] fails.

1 Introduction

The optimum compaction filters have been intensively investigated recently, e.g. in [1, 2, 3, 4, 5], mainly due to their applications to optimal coding gain filterbanks.

The optimization problem specifies the input correlation sequence, $r(1), r(3), \dots, r(2K - 1)$, and asks to find the FIR filter of order $2K - 1$ with maximum (or minimum) output variance, constrained such that the product filter $G(z) = H(z)H(z^{-1})$ is Nyquist(2), i.e. $g(2k) = 0, \forall k > 0$ and $g(0) = 1$. The output variance is

$$\sigma_y^2 = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} S(e^{j\omega})G(e^{j\omega})\frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \quad (1)$$

$$= r(0)g(0) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{2K-1} r(k)g(k) \quad (2)$$

and using the Nyquist(2) constraints the output variance results as

$$\sigma_y^2 = r(0) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^K r(2k-1)g(2k-1) \quad (3)$$

Our method to optimize (3) for the given $r(1), r(3), \dots, r(2K - 1)$ follows a simple construction: we conveniently extend the sequence

$r(1), r(3), \dots, r(2K - 1)$ to a correlation sequence $r_e(k), \forall k > 0$ such that the corresponding spectrum $S(e^{j\omega})$ is a line spectrum, and then simply force the polynomial $G(z)$ to have roots at the line frequencies and be a Nyquist(2) filter. If such a $G(z)$ exists, then it is the product filter corresponding to the global optimum compaction filter.

We start by looking for the following representation of the odd correlations $r(1), r(3), \dots, r(2K - 1)$:

$$r(2k-1) = \sum_{\ell=1}^{K_1} S_{\ell} \cos \omega_{\ell}(2k-1) \quad (4)$$

with $S_{\ell} > 0$ and $\omega_{\ell} \in [0, \pi]$, $\omega_{\ell} \neq \pi/2$. If such a representation exists the criterion (3) can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y^2 &= r(0) + 2 \sum_{k=1}^K r(2k-1)g(2k-1) \\ &= r(0) + \sum_{\ell=1}^{K_1} S_{\ell} \sum_{k=1}^K 2g(2k-1) \cos \omega_{\ell}(2k-1) \\ &= r(0) - \sum_{\ell=1}^{K_1} S_{\ell} + \sum_{\ell=1}^{K_1} S_{\ell} G(e^{j\omega_{\ell}}). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

To minimize (5) we have to associate with $S_{\ell} > 0$ the value $G(e^{j\omega_{\ell}}) = 0$ with double zeroes (since $G(z) = H(z)H(z^{-1})$) and supplementary, we have to impose the Nyquist(2) constraints to $G(z)$, all these requirements resulting in a linear system in the coefficients of $G(z)$. In the case when $G(e^{j\omega})$ is positive (or equivalently $G(z)$ can be factorized as $G(z) = H(z)H(z^{-1})$) it follows that $g(1), \dots, g(2K - 1)$ minimizes (5), hence being the optimal compaction product filter.

However, it may happen that $g(1), \dots, g(2K - 1)$ do not correspond to a positive $G(e^{j\omega})$, which means that the value σ_y^2 so obtained is only an upper bound, very similar in use with the bound established by the ideal (brickwall) filter, but now taking more information into account, i.e. the finiteness of the order $2K - 1$.

2 Approximation of Line Spectrum

The approximation of the line spectrum is based on the following simple observation:

Lemma 2.1 *There exists $S_\ell > 0$ and $\omega_\ell \in [0, \pi]$, $\omega_\ell \neq \pi/2$ such that (4) holds if and only if there exists $S_\ell \in \mathcal{R}$ and $\omega_\ell \in [0, \pi/2)$ such that (4) holds.*

Proof:

The Lemma follows from

$$S_\ell \cos((2k+1)(\pi - \omega_\ell)) = -S_\ell \cos((2k+1)\omega_\ell). \quad (6)$$

□

We will consider the representation of odd correlations (4) and introduce the coefficient vector $\underline{a}^T = [a_1 \ a_2 \ \dots \ a_{L_1}]$ ($L_1 \leq K$) of the polynomial

$$A(z) = 1 + a_1 z^{-1} + a_2 z^{-2} + \dots + a_{L_1} z^{-L_1} \quad (7)$$

having the nonreal roots $\{e^{\pm j2\omega_\ell}\}$ with $\omega_\ell \in (0, \pi/2)$ and if L_1 is odd a single real root 1.

Let us introduce an $L_1 \times L_1$ -matrix

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} r(1) & r(3) & \dots & r(2L_1 - 1) \\ r(1) & r(1) & \dots & r(2L_1 - 3) \\ r(3) & r(1) & \dots & r(2L_1 - 5) \\ r(5) & r(3) & \dots & r(2L_1 - 7) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ r(2L_1 - 3) & \dots & \dots & r(1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

and $L_1 \times 1$ -vectors

$$\underline{r}_1 = [r(1) \ r(3) \ \dots \ r(2L_1 - 1)]^T \quad (9)$$

and

$$\underline{r}_3 = [r(3) \ r(1) \ \dots \ r(2L_1 - 3)]^T. \quad (10)$$

When using all the information available, we have $L_1 = K$.

Lemma 2.2 *If there are S_ℓ, ω_ℓ with $S_\ell \in \mathcal{R}$, not necessarily positive, $\omega_\ell \in (0, \pi/2)$ such that (4) holds then $\underline{a}$ is a solution of all following linear systems:*

$$R\underline{a} = -\underline{r}_1 \quad (11)$$

$$(R + R^T)\underline{a} = -\underline{r}_1 - \underline{r}_3 \quad (12)$$

Proof:

Since all the roots of the polynomial (7) also have their inverses as roots, the polynomial (7) is symmetric or antisymmetric ($a_i = \pm a_{L_1-i}$, with $a_0 = 1$). Now we have for all the roots

$$1 + a_1 e^{j2\omega_\ell} + a_2 e^{j4\omega_\ell} + \dots + a_{L_1} e^{j2L_1\omega_\ell} = 0. \quad (13)$$

Let $\underline{a}' = [1 \ \underline{a}^T]^T$. Then the following identity holds for $\ell = 1, 2, \dots, (L_1 - 1)/2$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} e^{-j\omega_\ell} & e^{j\omega_\ell} & \dots & e^{j(2L_1-1)\omega_\ell} \\ e^{-j3\omega_\ell} & e^{-j\omega_\ell} & \dots & e^{j(2L_1-3)\omega_\ell} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ e^{-j(2L_1-1)\omega_\ell} & \dots & \dots & e^{j\omega_\ell} \end{bmatrix} \underline{a}' = \underline{0} \quad (14)$$

Writing it for the conjugate root $e^{-j\omega_\ell}$

$$\begin{bmatrix} e^{j\omega_\ell} & e^{-j\omega_\ell} & \dots & e^{-j(2L_1-1)\omega_\ell} \\ e^{j3\omega_\ell} & e^{j\omega_\ell} & \dots & e^{-j(2L_1-3)\omega_\ell} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ e^{j(2L_1-1)\omega_\ell} & \dots & \dots & e^{-j\omega_\ell} \end{bmatrix} \underline{a}' = \underline{0} \quad (15)$$

and adding all them up

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos \omega_\ell & \cos \omega_\ell & \dots & \cos (2L_1 - 1)\omega_\ell \\ \cos 3\omega_\ell & \cos \omega_\ell & \dots & \cos (2L_1 - 3)\omega_\ell \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cos (2L_1 - 1)\omega_\ell & \dots & \dots & \cos \omega_\ell \end{bmatrix} \underline{a}' = \underline{0}$$

Now multiply by S_ℓ and add to get (11). In passing we note that the unknown coefficients result from a linear system of equations of lower order as we have only $\lfloor (L_1 - 1)/2 \rfloor$ unknown coefficients due symmetry or antisymmetry.

To prove (12) note that identity $R^T \underline{a} = -\underline{r}_3$ can be proved similarly and combining both identities we get (12). □

Observation 2.1 *Using the fact (12) from above lemma, which implies that the solution we look for is also a solution of the symmetric Toeplitz system, and assuming that $2r(1), r(1) + r(3), \dots, r(2K - 3) + r(2K - 1)$ is positive definite, we could continue as in the analytical method [1].*

The frequencies ω_ℓ can be solved by finding the halves of the angles of the roots of polynomial (7). Then the corresponding S_ℓ can be found from a linear system of equations (4) with $K_1 = \lfloor (L_1 + 1)/2 \rfloor \leq \lfloor (K + 1)/2 \rfloor$ unknowns. This system of equations is overdetermined, but it will have an exact solution provided all the roots of the polynomial (7) are on the unit circle.

We thus obtained the representation (4) with $S_\ell \in \mathcal{R}$. Using the lemma 2.1 we find the representation with all the S_ℓ positive.

3 Summary of the Procedure

Our strategy for minimizing (3) can be summarized as follows:

1. Find the representation (4) of the correlation sequence $r(1), r(3), r(5), \dots, r(2K - 1)$ for the smallest value possible K_1 . The representation is defined by the set of values $\{\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_{K_1}\}$ and

$\{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_{K_1}\}$. Such a representation always exists for $K_1 = K$ but with our method if such a representation exists, $K_1 \leq \lfloor (K+1)/2 \rfloor$. If the representation does not exist the method fails.

2. Find $g_1, \dots, g_{2K}$, the coefficients of the polynomial

$$G(z) = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^K g_{2k-1}(z^{2k-1} + z^{-(2k-1)}), \quad (16)$$

using the following procedure:

(a) Construct the polynomial (K odd)

$$A_0(z) = (z^{-1} - 1) \prod_{\substack{\ell=1 \\ \omega_\ell \neq 0}}^{K_1} (z^{-2} - 2 \cos \omega_\ell z^{-1} + 1) \quad (17)$$

or the polynomial (K even)

$$A_0(z) = \prod_{\ell=1}^{K_1} (z^{-2} - 2 \cos \omega_\ell z^{-1} + 1) \quad (18)$$

and the Laurent polynomial

$$A(z) = A_0(z)A_0(z^{-1}) \quad (19)$$

(b) Find a Laurent polynomial

$$P(z) = p_0 + \sum_{k=1}^{K_p} p_k(z^{-k} + z^k) \quad (20)$$

such that $G(z) = P(z)A(z)$ satisfies Nyquist(2) condition and is of order $4K - 1$.

If $P(z)$ has all roots in reciprocal pairs, then continue with 3. If this is not the case, the method fails.

3. Factorize $P(z) = P_0(z)P_0(z^{-1})$, get $H_0(z) = P_0(z)A_0(z)$.

The analytical method [1] can find the optimum compaction filter only if the sequence $r(1) + r(1), r(1) + r(3), \dots, r(2K-3) + r(2K-1)$ is positive or negative definite. This corresponds to the case where the line frequencies in (4) (i.e. the angles of the roots on the unit of the optimal compaction filter $H(z)$) are all in either $[0, \pi/2)$ or in $(\pi/2, \pi)$, but not on both. In practice this means that when the analytical method presented in [1] is used the optimum compaction filters will be either low pass or high pass filters. In the new method, on the other hand, there is no such restriction. The only restriction in the location of the unit circle zeros of $H(z)$ is that for no $\omega_\ell \in [0, \pi/2)$ there can be a zero angle located both in ω_ℓ and $\pi - \omega_\ell$. But this constraint is general for any optimal compaction filter design method, and has a side result that there is no unique optimum compaction filter when the spectrum of the original signal is symmetrical around $\pi/2$.

4 An Analytical Example

We will go through an analytical example with the number of odd correlations $K = 2$. This example illustrates the conditions under which the optimum compaction filter can be found. The condition $\frac{r(3)}{r(1)} > -3$ is weaker than the positive definiteness of $\{r(1), r(3)\}$ (the latter holds if $1 > \frac{r(3)}{r(1)} > -1$) and also weaker than the positive definiteness of $\{2r(1), r(1) + r(3)\}$ (or, equivalently $1 > \frac{r(3)}{r(1)} > -3$).

Lemma 4.1 *If $\frac{r(3)}{r(1)} > -3$ there are $S_0 > 0$ and $\omega_0 \in [0, \pi)$ such that*

$$r(1) = S_0(e^{-j\omega_0} + e^{j\omega_0}) = 2S_0 \cos \omega_0 \quad (21)$$

$$r(3) = S_0(e^{-j3\omega_0} + e^{j3\omega_0}) = 2S_0 \cos 3\omega_0 \quad (22)$$

Proof: Letting

$$\cos \omega'_0 = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{r(1)}{3r(1) + r(3)}} \quad (23)$$

and

$$S'_0 = \text{sign}(r(1)) \sqrt{r(1)(3r(1) + r(3))} \quad (24)$$

and using the lemma 2.1 the parameters $S_0 > 0$ and $\omega_0 \in [0, \pi)$ are found. $\square$

The performance criterion becomes

$$\sigma_y^2 = r(0) - S_0 + S_0 G(e^{j\omega_0}) \quad (25)$$

Now $G(e^{j\omega_0}) = 0$ will minimize the criterion (25). A condition of the type $G(e^{j\omega_0}) = 0$ uniquely specifies the filter $G(e^{j\omega})$, since from the following system

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 \cos \omega_0 & 2 \cos 3\omega_0 \\ 2 \sin \omega_0 & 6 \sin 3\omega_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g(1) \\ g(3) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

we have the parameters of $G(z)$

$$\begin{aligned} g(1) &= -3/(6 \cos \omega_0 - 2 \cos 3\omega_0) \\ g(3) &= 1/(6 \cos \omega_0 - 2 \cos 3\omega_0) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

It remains to show that $G(e^{j\omega})$ is a valid product filter. The filter

$$G(z) = z^{-3}(g(3) + g(1)z^2 + z^3 + g(1)z^4 + g(3)z^6) \quad (28)$$

has the following zeros: $e^{j\omega_0}, e^{j\omega_0}, e^{-j\omega_0}, e^{-j\omega_0}$ and another couple of real zeros. In order to be able to factorize $G(z) = H(z)H(z^{-1})$ the other two zeros must be reciprocal and real: $z_5 = \rho, z_6 = 1/\rho$, which is always the case due to the symmetry of $G(z)$, except the unfavorable situation when $z_5 = 1, z_6 = -1$. For the latter to happen, both $2(g(1) + g(3)) = -1$ and $2(g(1) + g(3)) = 1$ must hold simultaneously which clearly is impossible. As a conclusion, the solution (27) always provides the optimum compaction filter.

Figure 1: Frequency spectra and magnitude response of the corresponding optimum compaction filters of order 15. Dotted - frequency spectrum, solid - the filter that maximizes compaction gain, dashdot - minimizes.

5 Simulations

Both analytical[1] and the new method were simulated in matlab using three different test correlation sequences. True frequency spectrum and amplitude responses of the corresponding optimum compaction filters of order 15 and 27 are shown in Figures 1 and 2 respectively.

For the first signal both the methods lead to same filters, but the optimum compaction filters corresponding to the second signal can only be found using the new method. For the third signal the optimum compaction filters that are found do not follow rapid changes in frequency spectrum. As we see, the transition bands get narrower when the order of the filter increases. Unfortunately, as the filter order increases there is also greater probability that the method fails due to numerical errors in the factorization procedures.

6 Conclusions

We have proposed a new design method for optimal compaction gain FIR filters. The analytical method presented in [1] can be easily shown to be a particular case in this framework, but our method finds the optimal solution in some of the cases when [1] fails. The difference in the methods is that the new method finds such optimum compaction filters that has zeros in both $[0, \pi/2)$ and $(\pi/2, \pi)$. In other words, the optimum compaction filters that can be found using the new method are not necessarily high pass or low pass filters.

The method contrasts with most of available methods, which are iterative in nature (based on linear programming or other constrained optimization techniques), in that it provides a fast and accurate non-iterative solution for many interesting practical situations. We also

Figure 2: Frequency spectra and magnitude response of the corresponding optimum compaction filters of order 27. Dotted - frequency spectrum, solid - the filter that maximizes compaction gain, dashdot - minimizes.

portrait the conditions under which the exact solution is found.

However, there are still situations where the new also method fails: 1) the representation (4) cannot be found for the odd correlations and 2) the polynomial $P(z)$ cannot be factorized. Also the numerical behavior becomes critical for high order filter, which is a general problem for all optimal compaction gain filter design methods.

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